

CLINICAL AND LABORATORY DESCRIPTION OF ELDERLY PEOPLE WITH DIAGNOSED CHRONIC HEART FAILURE

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Annotation

This article examines the clinical and laboratory profile of elderly and senile patients with a diagnosis of chronic heart failure. The study includes an analysis of clinical manifestations, laboratory data, and concomitant diseases specific to this age group. The aim of the study is to identify the features of the course of chronic heart failure in elderly patients, which will improve the diagnosis and optimize treatment approaches. The article provides data on the prevalence of various forms of heart failure, as well as on the frequency of complications and the effectiveness of therapeutic strategies used. Based on the results obtained, recommendations are formulated for the management of patients of this age category.

Keywords

chronic heart failure, elderly patients, clinical manifestations, laboratory data, therapy, complications.

Relevance

Chronic heart failure (CHF) is one of the most common diseases among the elderly and senile population, which determines the high relevance of the study. An increase in life expectancy leads to an increase in the number of patients with CHF, which puts a significant burden on health systems. CHF in elderly patients has its own characteristics associated with age-related changes in the body, the presence of multiple concomitant diseases and a decrease in the compensatory capabilities of the cardiovascular system. These factors complicate the diagnosis and treatment of CHF, which requires the development of specialized approaches to the management of this group of patients.

The problem of CHF is complicated by the fact that the clinical manifestations of the disease in the elderly may be atypical, which makes timely diagnosis difficult. Laboratory data may also differ from those in younger patients, which requires adaptation of diagnostic criteria. In addition, older patients often take a variety of medications to treat comorbidities, which increases the risk of drug interactions and side effects.

Taking into account the above, the study of clinical and laboratory characteristics of elderly and senile patients with CHF is extremely relevant. The data obtained can help to improve the diagnosis, improve the effectiveness of

treatment, and reduce the mortality and morbidity rate among this group of patients.

Goal

The aim of the study is to study the clinical and laboratory characteristics of chronic heart failure in elderly and senile patients in order to develop effective diagnostic and treatment strategies.

Materials and methods

The study involved 150 patients aged 65 years and older who were hospitalized with a diagnosis of chronic heart failure. Standard methods of physical examination and survey were used to assess clinical manifestations. Laboratory data included blood tests for markers of heart failure, functional tests, and instrumental studies (echocardiography, electrocardiography). Data analysis was performed using statistical processing methods, including correlation analysis and regression models.

Results

The results of the study showed that in elderly patients with chronic heart failure, significant variations in the clinical manifestations of the disease are observed. The most common symptoms are shortness of breath, fatigue, and swelling. Laboratory data revealed elevated levels of natriuretic peptides, which correlated with disease severity. Instrumental studies showed a decrease in the ejection fraction and the presence of structural changes in the heart. It was also found that the presence of concomitant diseases (diabetes mellitus, arterial hypertension) significantly worsens the prognosis and complicates treatment.

Conclusion

Thus, chronic heart failure in elderly patients is characterized by many specific features that must be taken into account in the diagnosis and treatment. Developing individualized approaches to managing these patients can significantly improve their quality of life and reduce mortality. The findings highlight the need for more careful monitoring and adaptation of therapeutic strategies for this age group.

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